

The xenobiotic sensor PXR in a marine flatfish species (*Solea senegalensis*): gene expression patterns and its regulation under different physiological conditions

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Abstract

The pregnane X receptor (PXR) is a nuclear receptor belonging to the NR1i sub-family and a known master regulator of xenobiotic metabolism. New roles have been recently proposed in mammals through its activation by vitamin K (VK) such as regulation of glucose metabolism, bone homeostasis, reproduction, neuronal development and cognitive capacities. In fish, particularly marine species, little is known about PXR and its potential roles. Here, expression patterns of *pxr* transcripts and conservation of protein domains were determined in the Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*), a marine flatfish model species in aquatic ecotoxicology. In addition to a full coding sequence transcript (*sspxr1*), two variants lacking DNA and/or ligand binding domains (*sspxr2* and *sspxr3*) were also identified. The expression of *sspxr1* during early development and in adult tissues was ubiquitous, but highest levels were observed in liver, intestine and skin. Expression was also detected by *in situ* hybridization in chondrocytes and cells from the granular and inner nuclear layers in three month old fish. Finally, *sspxr1* expression was shown to be differentially regulated under physiological conditions related with fasting, VK and warfarin metabolism. The present work provides new and basic knowledge regarding *pxr* sequence diversity and expression patterns in a marine flatfish species to unveil the potential impact of xenobiotics on fish physiology, and will allow a better and more ecosystemic environmental risk assessment of different pollutants over the marine environments with the development of reporter assays using PXR sequences from evolutionary distantly marine species.

Keywords: Pregnane X receptor; Xenobiotic sensor; Warfarin; Gene expression; Pollution; Evolutionary conservation; Senegalese sole *Solea senegalensis*

1. Introduction

Marine environments are the final sink of chemical compounds produced and/or released by anthropogenic activities, causing adverse developmental and reproductive effects (among others) in marine organisms. Among environmental pollutants, endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), exogenous substances that affect development, reproduction and/or metabolism, are of particular concern (reviewed in Diamanti-Kandarakis et al., 2009). EDCs can interfere with the endocrine system in a wide variety of ways, but mostly by modifying hormonal signaling mediated by nuclear receptors (NRs; Swedenborg et al., 2009). EDCs can also affect endocrine response by altering hormone metabolism through the activation of the pregnane X receptor (PXR; Mikamo et al., 2003).

The PXR is a member of the NR super-family NR1I (NR1I2), which includes the vitamin D receptor (VDR, NR1I1) and the constitutive androstane receptor (CAR, NR1I3; Willson and Kliewer, 2002). In mammals, *pxr* is expressed mainly in liver and intestine, but its transcripts have also been detected in cells of the osteoblastic lineage (Tabb et al., 2003). Although important physiological functions, including the control of glucose, lipid, cholesterol, bile acid and bilirubin homeostasis (Pavek 2016), as well as regulation of bone mineral density (Azuma et al., 2010), have been ascribed to PXR, it is still mostly recognized as a master regulator of genes involved in xenobiotic metabolism (Cheng et al., 2012). As a NR, PXR is a transcription factor activated by ligand binding that selectively modulates the transcription of genes showing specific response elements (REs) in promoter regions. In this sense, PXR (like any other NR) is characteristically composed by a DNA binding domain (DBD), involved in the binding to specific DNA sequences, a H (or hinge) region, enabling flexible conformations of the DBD and the ligand binding domain (LBD), and a C-terminal LBD, where the

ligands are bound (Blumberg et al., 1998). In an evolutionary perspective, although PXR has a highly conserved DBD, it is not the case of its LBD, exhibiting the lowest degree of conservation among the NRs (Ekins et al., 2007). Furthermore, PXR has a LBD highly flexible and forms a binding cavity substantially larger than that of many other NRs, enabling the binding of a wide range of small endogenous and exogenous molecules (Wu et al., 2013; Pavék 2016). Among those, warfarin enantiomers have the ability to bind directly to PXR (Rulcova et al., 2010). Warfarin is an anticoagulant drug used worldwide as a rodenticide, causing lethal hemorrhages in rats and mice, and is considered an emerging contaminant negatively impacting the natural environment (Lao and Gan et al., 2012). It might also have a high impact on off-target species such as birds when they eat poisoned rodents (Watanabe et al., 2010), or aquatic organisms when released to the environment (Fernandez et al., 2014).

Current regulatory eco-toxicity testing implies the use of different organisms and alternative (*in vitro* and *in silico*) methods in order to assess the risk of releasing chemical compounds to the environment. In this sense, these and other (e.g. quantitative structure–activity relationship (QSAR)) methods to study the interaction of different chemicals with NRs will allow to predict its action and environmental risk assessment (le Maire et al., 2010). An increased understanding on PXR activation by different compounds (Ekins et al., 2007, 2008), transcriptional regulation (Kurose et al., 2006; Tompkins et al., 2008; Kubota et al., 2015), downstream PXR-target genes (Kandel et al., 2016), PXR-crosstalk with other signaling pathways (Pavék 2016), and on the function of transcript variants (Koyano et al., 2004; Lamba et al., 2004; Brewer and Chen, 2016) has been achieved in mammalian species. However, information from non-mammalian species is limited. In aquatic organisms, PXR has been mostly studied in the zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), a widely used freshwater model species for developmental

biology (Goldsmith and Jobin, 2012) and toxicology (Raldúa et al., 2012). Expression patterns of *pxr* have been fragmentally studied using PCR and quantitative real time PCR (qPCR; Maglich et al., 2003; Bresolin et al., 2005; Bainy et al., 2013; Fernandez et al., 2014; Fernandez et al., 2015) or by *in situ* hybridization (Bertrand et al., 2007), while ligand activation was explored using luciferase reporter assays (Reschly et al., 2007; Ekins et al., 2008; Krasowski et al., 2011; Bainy et al., 2013). Information in marine organisms is scarce and limited to the sea squirt (*Ciona intestinalis*; Fidler et al., 2012; Richter and Fidler, 2015), the peppery furrow shell (*Scrobicularia plana*; Cruzeiro et al., 2016), the Japanese puffer (*Takifugu rubripes*; Maglich et al., 2003), the killifish (*Fundulus heteroclitus*; Gräns et al., 2015) and the Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*; Richard et al., 2014; partial sequence). Since PXR-related pollutant effect largely depends on its LBD sequence, when and where it is expressed, getting basic knowledge on full PXR sequences in several marine species (both vertebrates and invertebrates) to develop reporter assays will allow a more accurate and ecosystemic approaches of environmental risk assessment.

Senegalese sole is a marine flatfish species that has been previously used in ecotoxicology. In this sense, flatfish have been targeted for biomonitoring programs of coastal ecosystems, in part owing to their benthic behavior, which makes them suitable sentinels for the monitoring of marine sediments (Gonçalves et al., 2014). Knowledge on optimal husbandry practices and environmental conditions, genetic background and/or nutrition have recently been gained for the Senegalese sole (Morais et al., 2014), allowing their production in captivity and strengthening their suitability as model species in toxicology (Oliva et al., 2012; Solé et al., 2016; among others).

The present research aimed at getting basic information on: i) mRNA and protein sequences to ease *in silico* studies toward the prediction of the interaction

between Senegalese sole PXR and chemical compounds; ii) levels and sites of *pxr* expression during early development and in adult tissues to provide clues about the potential effects of exposure to known (or still to be uncovered) PXR xenobiotic agonists; and iii) how its expression is regulated under different physiological conditions to study its suitability as a reliable biomarker.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Ethics statement

Fish facilities and persons in charge of animal experimentation were all accredited by the Portuguese National Authority for Animal Health (DGAV) and all experimental procedures involving animals followed the European Directive 2010/63/EU, the related guidelines (European Commission, 2014) and the Portuguese legislation (Decreto-Lei 113/2013) for animal experimentation and welfare.

2.2 Senegalese sole larval rearing and sampling

Senegalese sole eggs were obtained from natural spawning of broodstocks at the Aquaculture Research Station of EPPO/IPMA (Olhão, Portugal) and transferred to the fish facilities at the CCMAR - University of Algarve (Faro, Portugal). After thermal, light and chemical acclimatization, eggs were incubated in a semi-closed water recirculating system equipped with mechanical and biological filters, protein skimmer and a UV sterilizer. After hatching, the larvae were randomly distributed into four 100-L white cylindro-conical tanks at a density of 95 larvae L⁻¹. After settlement (19 days post hatch; dph), post-larvae were transferred to three liter flat bottom plastic trays (120 larvae per tray). Environmental parameters were: 19.9 ± 1.2°C, 36.9 ± 1.2 g L⁻¹

salinity, 97.6 ± 4.9 % dissolved oxygen saturation, 12h light: 12h dark photoperiod and 900 lux light intensity at water surface.

Larvae were progressively fed, three times a day, with live preys: rotifers (*Brachionus rotundiformis*) from 2 to 10 dph, *Artemia* nauplii (AF strain; Salt Lake) from 6 to 10 dph and *Artemia* metanauplii (EG strain; Salt Lake) enriched with Red PepperTM (Bernaqua, Belgium) from 9 to 17 dph. The same *Artemia* metanauplii, but immediately frozen after enrichment, were provided to the larvae from 18 dph until the 30 dph. Larvae were then progressively weaned onto inert diet specifically designed for Senegalese sole by Sparos Lda (Olhão, Portugal) and supplemented with 125 mg kg^{-1} dry weight (DW) of phylloquinone (125VK₁ diet) until three months.

Fish previously euthanized with an overdose of Tricaine methanesulfonate (MS-222, Sigma-Aldrich) were sampled and washed with sterile distilled water. Embryonic stages were sampled at 13.5, 18.5, 24, 36 (hatching) and 48 hours post-fertilization (hpf), while larval and juvenile stages were sampled at 2, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 16, 20, 24 and 30 dph. For each biological replicate, 60 eggs (at 13.5, 18.5 and 24 hpf), up to 20 larvae (at 36 hpf, 2,5, 7, 9, 11, 13 and 16 dph) or 5 juveniles (at 20, 24 and 30 dph) were pooled depending on their size, preserved in TRI-Reagent (Ambion) and stored at -80 °C until processed for RNA extraction.

2.3 Senegalese sole adult fish maintenance and tissues sampling

Adult fish from the Aquaculture Research Station of EPPO/IPMA (Olhão, Portugal) were transferred to the fish facilities at the CCMAR. After thermal, light and chemical acclimatization during 15 days in a semi-closed water recirculating system, fish were euthanized and sampled. Several tissues (spleen, eye, brain, testis, ovary, muscle, bone, skin, liver, heart, kidney, branchial arches and intestine) were sampled and pooled from

3-5 adult fish (mixed females and males, except for gonads). Tissues collected for gene expression analysis were placed in TRI-Reagent and stored at -80 °C until processed.

2.4 Exposure of Senegalese sole juveniles to different physiological conditions

Senegalese sole juveniles aged 55 dph (with 80 ± 7 mg wet weight (WW) and 14.91 ± 1.79 mm of standard length) grown under standard rearing procedures were distributed into 4 experimental flat bottom plastic trays (40 specimens per tray) and further cultured under the environmental conditions previously described. Juveniles were initially fed with 125 mg kg^{-1} DW VK₁ inert diet (125VK₁ diet) at 3 % WW during 5 days, then i) continuously fed with 125VK₁ diet for 5 days (Control group), ii) fasting during 2 days (Fasting group) and re-fed for 3 days with VK₁ supplemented diet (1250 mg kg^{-1} DW, 1250VK₁ diet; Refeed group), iii) fed with 125VK₁ diet and exposed to 25 mg L^{-1} of warfarin (3-(*a*-acetylbenzyl)-4-hydroxycoumarin sodium salt; Sigma-Aldrich) during 2 days (Warfarin group) and re-fed for 3 days with 1250VK₁ diet while still exposed to warfarin (Warfarin rescue group), or iv) continuously fed with 1250VK₁ diet for 5 days (VK₁+ group). Individual fish were sampled in triplicate from each experimental group at 2 and 5 days after each treatment initiated, euthanized with an overdose of MS-222, washed with sterile distilled water and stored in TRI-Reagent at -80 °C until RNA extraction.

2.5 Construction of Senegalese sole cDNA libraries

Total RNA (2 µg) isolated from different larval stages, juvenile and adult fish tissues (see below) was pooled and used to construct a cDNA library using the Marathon cDNA amplification kit (Clontech) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.6 3'- and 5'-RACE PCR

Degenerated primers used to amplify Senegalese sole *pxr* were designed in conserved regions of fish *pxr* sequences retrieved from GenBank database (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) using on-site BLAST facilities. A partial internal cDNA sequence was obtained and used to design specific primers to amplify the full-length sequence by RACE PCR using the Marathon cDNA amplification kit. Specific primers for gene expression quantification and *in situ* hybridization probes synthesis were also designed. The sequence of all the primers used in this work are presented in Table 1.

2.7 Phylogenetic reconstruction and PXR amino acid sequence analysis

Nuclear receptor subfamily 1, group I, member 1, 2 and 3 protein sequences (42 in total; Supplementary table 1) retrieved from GenBank database were used to construct the phylogeny tree. In most cases, protein sequences were gathered using on-site BLASTp tool with position-specific iterated BLAST (PSI-BLAST; Altschul et al., 1997) algorithm. Sequences were aligned using ClustalW software (www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalw2) (Larkin et al., 2007) and analyzed using MEGA version 7 to construct a molecular phylogeny (Kumar, et al 2016). Maximum Likelihood tree was created using a Poisson correction model and a gamma distribution with site rate variation, and gaps were considered as partial deletion. For branching support, 500 bootstrap replications were analyzed. PXR percentage identity matrixes were calculated using ClustalW software. PXR binding domains were determined using Pfam v.28.0 signatures and Conserved Domain Database (CDD; ncbi.nlm.nih.gov). Sequence of *Caenorhabditis elegans* nuclear hormone receptor (NHR)-1 ([NP_001024855](http://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/NP_001024855)) was used as outgroup in PXR phylogeny. A T-Coffee alignment of PXR sequences was used to analyze the conservation of the protein domains throughout

evolution (www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/tcoffee/), while resources of InterPro (www.ebi.ac.uk/interpro) (Quevillon et al., 2005) were used to predict DNA binding and ligand binding domains (DBD and LBD, respectively) and other features of Senegalese sole PXR.

2.8 RNA extraction and PCR conditions

Total RNA was extracted from embryos, larvae, juveniles and/or adult tissues stored in TRI-Reagent following manufacturer instructions and purified using the High Pure RNA Isolation kit (Roche Applied Science). RNA integrity was confirmed using Experion Automated Electrophoresis system (Bio-Rad) and quantity was determined using NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific). Total RNA (1 µg) was reverse-transcribed for 1 h at 37°C, using M-MLV reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen), oligo-d(T) universal primer and RNase OUT (Invitrogen).

Quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) reactions were performed in triplicates using SsoFast EVAgreen Supermix (Bio-Rad), 0.25 µM of isoform-specific primers (Table 1) and 1:10 dilution of reverse transcribed RNA, in the StepOnePlus Real-Time PCR system (Applied Biosystems). PCR amplification was as follows: an initial denaturation step of 1 min at 95°C and 40 cycles of amplification (5 s at 95°C and 10 s at 65°C). A calibrator sample (cDNA pooled from all samples) was included in each qPCR plate (Derveaux et al., 2010). Efficiency of amplification was between 95-106% for all primer sets. Levels of gene expression were calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ comparative method and normalized using *Ubiquitin (Ubiq)* RNA levels (Infante et al., 2008). Gene expression at 18.5 hpf, in ovaries and in Control group were set to 1 and used as reference samples for relative expression during development, in adult tissues and the experimental exposures, respectively.

Transcript variants were identified in adult tissues through standard PCR using Platinum[®] PCR SuperMix High Fidelity (Invitrogen), following manufacturer's recommendations. Equal amounts of PCR product were run in 2% agarose gels of ethidium bromide. Size of amplified bands were identified using Gene Ruler 100 bp Plus Ladder (Thermo Scientific) and observed under UV light. Images were obtained by UVP Doc-It LS Image Acquisition Software.

2.9 In situ hybridization and histological analysis

Fish aged 3 months were sampled as previously described, fixed for 24 h at 4 °C in 4% paraformaldehyde (pH 7.4, in PBS), washed 3 × 10 min with PBS and decalcified during one week at 4 °C in 10% EDTA (pH 7.4, in DEPC water). Samples were dehydrated through a PBS/methanol gradient and stored in 100% methanol at -20 °C. When appropriate, fish were passed through an increasing methanol/xylol series, embedded in paraffin then cross-sectioned. Sections (5-7-µm thick) were collected on TESPA (3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane, Sigma–Aldrich) coated slides or Superfrost Plus slides (VWR), dried for 4 h at 37 °C and kept at -20 °C until used.

Consecutive decalcified sections were either submitted to histological or *in situ* hybridization procedures. Histological samples were stained with Haematoxylin-Eosin as described by Martoja and Martoja-Pierson (1970) to provide a clear identification of the different tissues. For *in situ* hybridization, sense and antisense RNA probes were generated from 1 µg of linearized plasmid containing a 420-bp PXR sequence using T7 or SP6 polymerases then labelled with digoxigenin-dUTP (DIG RNA labeling kit, Roche Diagnostics). Riboprobes were treated with RNase-free DNase, recovered through ethanol precipitation and their integrity was assessed through agarose gel electrophoresis. Preparation of sections and *in situ* hybridization were performed using

a modified protocol previously described by Pinto et al. (2003). Briefly, sections were hybridized at 68 °C for 16-18 h with 400 ng of riboprobe, then incubated with a 1:2000 dilution of anti-digoxigenin-alkaline phosphatase antibody (Roche Diagnostics) and signal was revealed using NBT/BCIP (Sigma-Aldrich) as substrate. Images were taken using an Axio Imager Z2 microscope (Carl Zeiss) coupled with a digital AxioCam camera.

2.10 Statistical analysis

Results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. All data were checked for normality (Kolmogorov–Smirnov test) and homoscedasticity of variance (Bartlett's test). Significant differences in gene expression were detected by one-way ANOVA and Tukey multiple-comparison test during early development and in adult tissues and by Student's t-test in juveniles exposed to different physiological conditions. Differences were considered to be significant for $P < 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed using Prims 5.0 (GraphPad Software, Inc.).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Senegalese sole PXR exhibits features of the NR1I subfamily

Partial sequence previously amplified (Richard et al., 2014), using degenerated primers (designed in conserved regions), was extended by Rapid Amplification of cDNA Ends (RACE) PCR to get the full-length sequence of Senegalese sole *pxr* (*sspxr*). A 1916-bp long sequence, encoding a 431 amino acid peptide (*ssPXR1*), was cloned and deposited in GenBank database (Accession number KC108909).

A phylogenetic analysis of the NR1i super-family revealed that *ssPXR1* sequence clustered with other teleost PXR independently from VDR and CAR

sequences, and probably represents the orthologous sequence in this species (Fig. 1). Previous molecular phylogenies of the NR1i super-family proposed that VDR, PXR and CAR sequentially evolved from a common ancestor represented by *Ciona intestinalis* VDR/PXR (Reschly et al., 2007; Ekins et al., 2008; Bainy et al., 2013). Of note, the position of PXR sequences from frogs (*Xenopus laevis* and *Xenopus tropicalis*) between CAR and PXR sequences of other vertebrates was consistent with the already reported differences in function, tissue expression, and sequence (Ekin et al., 2008).

Comparative analysis of PXR sequences revealed a variable percent identity in ssPXR1 when the complete peptide (Supplementary Table 2), the DBD (Supplementary Table 3) or the LBD (Supplementary Table 4) were individually considered. While percent ID was low at the scale of the full peptide (from 42 to 86%) and the LBD (from 49 to 92%) sequences, it was higher when only the DBD was considered (from 63 to 96%). Lower conservation of LBD in ssPXR1 was in agreement with the extensive sequence divergence observed across species (Bainy et al., 2013; Gräns et al., 2015) and the different ligand selectivity proposed (Reschly et al., 2007; Ekins et al., 2008). In this regard, amino acids critical to DBD and LBD structure/function in human PXR (Östberg et al., 2002; Timsit and Negishi, 2007; Lin et al., 2009; Tsuji 2014; Wallace et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2013) were conserved in ssPXR1 (Fig. 2), including the 8 cysteine residues (33C, 36C, 50C, 53C, 69C, 75C, 85C, 88C) responsible for the Zinc binding sites, the 13 residues (43Y, 44H, 45F, 51E, 52G, 54K, 58R, 59R, 82R, 83R, 89R, 103V, 104M) involved in DNA binding, and the 5 residues (70P, 71F, 84S, 101D, 102M) composing the dimer interface. Similarly, several residues central to the formation of PXR-RXR heterodimers in human (315P, 345D, 356D, 359H, 367K, 384P, 385K, 387V, 391T, 392E, 394R, 398E; Wallace et al., 2013), to the structure of ligand binding site morphology (234H, 235M, 238L, 239T, 242M, 277Q, 280F, 291W, 298Y, 302D,

303G, 308F, 312L, 313L, 316L, 400Y) and to the recognition of coactivators (247I, 251K, 257R, 264Q, 265I, 268L, 269K, 418L, 421E, 422V) were also conserved in ssPXR1 LBD. Present data confirmed the higher conservation of DBD and the divergence on the LBD in PXR throughout evolution (Krasowski et al., 2005; Reschly et al., 2007; Ekins et al., 2008).

DBD and LBD are defining features of NRs, allowing their binding to particular DNA motifs to initiate gene transcription and their activation by ligand binding, respectively (Willson and Kliewer, 2002; Tsuji 2014). Any alteration in DBD and LBD sequences, e.g. through alternative splicing events, would alter PXR activity. The occurrence of *pxr* transcript variants in Senegalese sole was demonstrated with the amplification of two sequences of 676 bp (*sspxr2*; accession number KY614146) and 262 bp (*sspxr3*; accession number KY614147) using cds-specific primers (Fig. 3a). While all *sspxr* variants were found to be expressed in the intestine, only *sspxr2* and *sspxr3* were found in the ovary of adult Senegalese sole by end-point PCR. Alignment of the three transcripts showed that a large part of the coding sequence was missing in *sspxr2* and *sspxr3*, an event probably resulting from the splicing of several exons (Supplementary Figure 1). While PXR2 is a 215 amino acid peptide lacking the complete LBD, PXR3 is a 65 amino acid peptide lacking the complete DBD and most of the LBD sequences (Fig. 3b).

Single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) have been detected in mammalian and zebrafish PXR genes (Lamba et al., 2004; Koyano et al., 2004; Bainy et al., 2013) and spliced variants have been also reported in breast, hepatic and intestinal tissues of mammalian species (Lamba et al., 2004; Brewer and Chen 2016). Transcript variants were found to be differentially expressed in some tissues with functional consequences such as reduced or total loss of transactivation activity of known target genes (Koyano

et al., 2004; Matic et al., 2010; Brewer and Chen 2016). The generation of transcript variants through alternative splicing is a strategy commonly used to produce NR isoforms that can differ in structure and functional properties (Keightley, 1998). Splicing variants hPXR.2 and hPXR.3 (human) and mPXR.var (mouse) are missing exon 5 (due to the presence of cryptic AG splice sites in this exon) and peptides have a shorter LBD (Kliewer et al., 1998; Lamba et al., 2004). Human variant hPXR.4 is missing part of exon 2 and has a shorter DBD (Fukuen et al., 2002; Lamba et al., 2004). Since Senegalese sole genome is still not known, an inferred distribution of nucleotide/amino acid sequences in exons using the most close related fish species with known genome allowed us to identify to which exons the deletions on ssPXR2 and 3 were related. Deletions originating ssPXR2 and 3 started at exon 5 and exon 2 (respectively) of the inferred ssPXR gene (Supplementary figure 1), suggesting a conservation of alternative splicing events in vertebrates. While the biological function of ssPXR3 (lack of the DBD and most of the LBD) is somehow obscure, PXR2 (lack of the LBD) may still have the ability to interact with DNA and act as a transcriptional repressor or mediate constitutive transcription in absence of ligand binding, as it was demonstrated for hPXR.3 (Lin et al., 2009). It is also highly probable that ssPXR2 and ssPXR3 are unable to bind ligands, similarly to hPXR.3 and hPXR.4 (Lamba et al., 2004).

3.2 Larval development, cell and tissue dependent expression of ssPXR1

Since only ssPXR1 peptide has the complete LBD, toxic events through disrupted PXR signaling due to the binding of pollutants to this NR might only occur when and where this variant is expressed. Therefore the expression of *sspxr1* transcript was explored by qPCR.

Senegalese sole larvae undergo metamorphosis during early ontogeny, a highly complex transition process necessary to the adaptation of flatfish larvae from an initial pelagic behavior to a final benthic one. It is an endocrine driven process (Pittman et al., 2013) that involves a set of profound morphological, biochemical and physiological transformations (Geffen 2007). During embryonic development (Fig. 4), *spxr1* expression was first detected at 18.5 hours post-fertilization, and levels increased until mouth opening (3 dph). Afterwards, *spxr1* expression remained low until the onset of metamorphosis (9 dph) but increased progressively during pre-metamorphosis, reaching highest levels at pro-metamorphosis independently of the pelagic (16 dph) or benthic (16 dph*) behavior exhibited by Senegalese sole larvae. At 20 dph, when Senegalese sole completed the eye migration process, *spxr1* expression was again low but increased shortly afterwards at 24 dph. At 30 dph, Senegalese sole completed the metamorphosis process and showed an intermediate value of gene expression. A similar pattern of *pxr* expression has recently been reported during the early development of zebrafish (Fernandez et al., 2014), remaining low during embryogenesis and reaching a peak at mouth opening. High levels of gene expression at this stage may be related to organogenesis events, as suggested by *in situ* hybridization data in zebrafish (Bertrand et al., 2007). The higher levels of *spxr1* expression during metamorphosis and particularly the peak at pro-metamorphosis might also be related to the above mentioned morphological, biochemical and physiological transformations that occur in the different organs at this critical stage and related processes such as the pituitary development, cranial and visceral skeleton re-arrangement, eye migration, skin pigmentation development (with a climax at molecular level at 14 and 16 dph) or digestive system (liver, pancreas and intestinal) maturation (Sæle et al., 2006; Zambonino-Infante et al. 2008; Darias et al., 2011; Padros et al., 2011; Pittman et al.,

2013), among others. The expression of *spxr1* in several of these organs has been confirmed by qPCR in adult fish (Fig. 5). Highest levels of expression were found in the liver, followed in order of magnitude by the intestine, skin, spleen, heart, branchial arches and brain, and to a much lesser extent in muscle, kidney, testis, ovaries, eyes and vertebral tissues. High expression levels in the liver and intestine was consistent with expression data reported in mouse and human (Lehmann et al., 1998) and also with its function as a master xenobiotic sensor. The broad distribution of *spxr1* expression in tissues was also in agreement with the expression data reported for *pxr* in mammals and other fish species (zebrafish and Fugu; Maglich et al., 2003; Lamba et al., 2004; Bainy et al., 2013; Fernandez et al., 2014; Gräns et al., 2015) but also with those of its most likely ancestor VDR/PXR in marine invertebrates (Richter and Fidler, 2015). In a general manner, the ubiquitous expression of *pxr* in vertebrate tissues is compatible with the hypothesis that tissue-specific ligands of PXR are present in these tissues and/or with the involvement of PXR-target genes in functions other than detoxification, e.g. steroid metabolism (Ekins et al., 2008), brain development (Bertrand et al., 2007) or gametogenesis (Gray and Squires, 2012). In this sense, in order to gain further insights on the specific sites where *pxr* is expressed and regulate gene transcription through its binding to DNA sequences, a probe recognizing transcript variants *spxr1* and *spxr2* was designed in the region coding for DBD domain.

Sites of *spxr1* and/or *spxr2* expression (from now on *spxr*) were determined in 3-months old Senegalese sole juveniles through *in situ* hybridization (ISH) of histological sections. No differentiated ovary and testis were observed in these juveniles probably because they did not undergo sexual differentiation yet. Although Viñas et al. (2013) showed that females are already differentiated at 98 dpf and males are clearly identified at 127 dpf, Blanco-Vives et al. (2011) only distinguished males from females

at 110 dph. Discrepancies regarding the timing of sexual differentiation could be related to differences in the size of the fish sampled, consequence of the use of different rearing conditions and/or feeding protocols.

Expression of *sspxr* was detected in different tissues of the cranial region such as the brain (Fig. 6a). Expression of *pxr* in the brain has already been reported in mammalian and fish species (Lamba et al., 2004; Bertrand et al., 2007) as well as its activation by neurosteroids such as pregnanes (the prototypical ligands for the “pregnane X receptor”) or nicotine (Lamba et al., 2004). Senegalese sole *pxr* expression was detected in the granular layer (Fig. 6a and b), a densely packed layer containing mossy fibers, the cell bodies of granule cells, uni-polar brush cells, and Golgi cells. This layer represents a complex communication network between its own cells and those from other brain (outer) layers (Purkinje and molecular layers). Since cells from the granular layer releases the neurotransmitter glutamate (Spruston and McBain, 2006), this tissue was associated with effective hippocampal-dependent memory function and possibly to spatial exploration (Chawla and Barnes 2007). Thus, present results suggest that xenobiotics capable of activating ssPXR may have a neurotoxic impact on brain development and locomotor capacities in fish species.

ISH data also indicated that *sspxr* is present in specific cell layers within the eye (Fig. 6c and d). A strong signal was observed in the inner nuclear layer (In), while a less intense signal was revealed in the nerve fiber layer (Nfl) and the rod nucleus (Rn). Thinning of the In and thickening of the Nfl have been associated with night blindness (Al Oreany et al., 2016), and glaucoma and retinal diseases (Pasol 2011), respectively. While the expression of several NRs has been detected in the developing fish eye (Bertrand et al., 2007), *sspxr* was observed in a fully developed eye (present work and

Fernandez et al., 2014), suggesting that ssPXR would rather play a homeostatic role in fish eye rather than being involved in its development.

Expression of *sspXR* was also found in adjacent mesenchymal tissue (Fig. 6e) and chondrocytes (Fig. 6f) of cell rich hyaline cartilages as well as at the neural arch insertion, and also in osteoblasts of the neural spines and vertebral bodies (Fig. 7a and b). Expression of *sspXR* in these skeletal tissues is consistent with the proposed role of PXR in the maintenance of mammalian bone (Azuma et al., 2010), where it regulates the expression of key genes in bone development and extracellular matrix mineralization (Tabb et al., 2003).

Finally, *sspXR* expression was detected in the digestive and hematopoietic systems although to different extents. Both intense and diffuse signals were observed in the intestinal epithelium and in the liver (Fig. 7c). While the intensity of the expression was region-related in the intestine, the strong expression in the liver was clearly associated to the exocrine pancreas (Fig. 7c and d). Among hematopoietic tissues, strong signals were observed in the spleen (Fig. 7e) and the kidney (Fig. 7f). While *sspXR* expression in the digestive system was in agreement with the reported transactivation of PXR by the bile acids (Ekins et al., 2008) and the transcription of genes encoding enzymes involved in the digestion and lipid metabolism (Bitter et al., 2015); expression in the spleen and kidney may be related with a role of PXR in the control of detoxification processes such as the clearing of blood from wastes and potentially toxic intermediates (e.g. cholic acid; reviewed by Tovar-Palacio et al., 2012).

Previously published ISH data already revealed *pxr* expression in brain (pituitary, telencephalon and diencephalon), liver and intestinal bulb (Bertrand et al., 2007) of developing zebrafish (up to 48 hpf). Nevertheless, present data in a marine flatfish expanded the basic knowledge in a later stage of development, providing

insights on the cell types expressing *sspxr*, tissues possibly targeted by xenobiotic toxic effects and/or where exerted a particular transcriptional control.

*3.3 Expression of *sspxr1* is regulated by specific physiological conditions*

Consequences of PXR activation can be both beneficial and harmful to the organism. While the activation of PXR positively accelerates the detoxification process and consequently the elimination of xenobiotics, it can also negatively alter the metabolism of compounds (e.g. hormones) required for normal physiological functions (le Marie et al., 2010). The metabolism of inactive compounds through PXR signaling can also lead to active metabolites synthesis such as the transformation of synthetic organochlorine methoxychlor into xenoestrogen, resulting in the alteration of the estrogen receptor signaling (Mikamo et al., 2003). In addition, several compounds have been described to activate or not PXR in a species-dependent manner, e.g. the rifampicin activates the human PXR, but not the zebrafish and green-spotted pufferfish (*Tetraodon nigroviridis*) PXR (Ekins et al., 2008; Krasowski et al., 2011). Furthermore, differences in *pxr* gene expression in liver and gills of killifish from two different populations (from a site highly polluted with polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and a reference site) was previously reported when exposed to PCB 126 and PCB 153 (Gräns et al., 2015). Since reliable biomarkers of pollution has to be specific to pollutant exposure (Hook et al., 2014), whether *pxr* gene expression is affected by other conditions than the presence of xenobiotics in the media was explored. In this sense, *sspxr1* expression was evaluated in Senegalese sole reared under relevant physiological conditions in natural environments (fasting, re-feeding, nutritional deficiency or supplementation on vitamin K (VK); Fig. 8) in order to evaluate the potential use of this approach as a reliable biomarker of pollutant exposure.

Early juveniles unfed for two days and then re-fed for three days showed an increased *spxr* expression in comparison with control conditions (fish fed with 125VK₁ diet; Fig. 8). Under starvation/fasting, marine fish undergo dramatic changes in metabolism (Santulli et al., 1997), with particular variations in triglycerides reported in the Senegalese sole (Costas et al., 2011) and the common dentex (*Dentex dentex*; Perez-Jimenez et al., 2012). Under fasting conditions, a more pronounced depletion of lipid stores in the viscera rather than in other organs, such as muscle has been demonstrated (Storebakken et al., 1991), with triglycerides and phospholipids being reconstituted in the intestinal epithelium (Santulli et al., 1997). Thus, an increased *spxr1* expression in soles under fasting conditions is consistent with the transcription control reported for PXR over the genes encoding enzymes involved in digestion and lipid metabolism (Bitter et al., 2015) but also with the expression data reported here showing *spxr1* expression in the intestine and liver. Lipids stored in the viscera are probably mobilized to counteract food deprivation. This mobilization may result in the transport of lipophilic pollutants present in lipid-storing tissues to other tissues/organs (e.g. liver and brain), where they could cause adverse effects (Jørgensen et al., 2006). Furthermore, expression of *spxr1* remained high in soles re-fed for three days, which might be related with the reported transient period of metabolic adjustments directed toward the physiological condition restoration (Perez-Jimenez et al., 2012).

Warfarin, a rodenticide commonly used worldwide, is considered an emerging pollutant and a threat to the natural environment due to secondary poisoning episodes in raptors (Watanabe et al., 2010) and/or its release in aquatic environments (Fernandez et al., 2014). The R-warfarin enantiomer has been identified as a ligand of PXR (Rulcova et al., 2010). An up-regulation of *spxr1* expression was observed in Senegalese sole juveniles exposed to 25 mg L⁻¹ of warfarin during two days, while levels similar to

those in Control group were found in juveniles fed with 1250VK₁ diet during warfarin exposure (Fig. 8). Higher expression of *sspxr1* in soles exposed to warfarin and a rescue by VK₁ supplementation is consistent with data collected in zebrafish (Fernandez et al., 2014 and 2015). Although it remains to be experimentally confirmed, present results suggested that warfarin has the ability to bind ssPXR1 and could impact marine fish species in a way similar to the effect reported in freshwater species (Fernandez et al., 2014). In this sense, while 25 mg L⁻¹ of warfarin was found to induce pathological calcification in zebrafish heart (Fernandez et al., 2014), contradictory data on the prevalence of warfarin in the environment have been reported (between a half-life of 7 days till being detected after 3 years of treatment). Since it is used continuously in palm oil and rice fields from underdeveloped countries (up to 3543 kg ha⁻¹; Wood and Fee, 2003), it constitutes a permanent source of contamination for aquatic ecosystems by surface run-off.

Expression of *sspxr1* in Senegalese sole juveniles fed with a VK₁ rich (1250VK₁) diet (10 times more VK₁ than the Control 125VK₁ diet) during two days was increased in comparison to levels determined in Control group. Surprisingly, *sspxr1* expression was similar in soles fed 5 days with the 1250VK₁ diet and those fed with the Control diet (Fig. 8). These results are in contradiction with those reported in Senegalese sole larvae fed increasing levels of VK₁ dietary content (Richard et al., 2014), where a decrease in *sspxr1* expression was observed at the end of a 36 days feeding trial. Differences in duration of the nutritional feeding trial or the developmental stage used in both studies may explain these discrepancies. Expression patterns observed in this study in fish fed for 2 and 5 days with increased dietary VK₁ content may indicate a progressive adaptation of Senegalese sole metabolism to the new/increased nutritional amount of VK, a reported ligand of PXR (Tabb et al., 2003).

A feedback loop regulatory mechanism has already been reported for PXR when stimulated by lithocholic acid (another endogenous ligand of PXR), where ligand activation of PXR suppressed the transcription of the *pxr* gene (Bailey et al., 2011).

Variable transcript levels in fish submitted to different physiological conditions suggest that *pxr* gene expression may not be a suitable biomarker for on-field monitoring programs (or when nutritional condition of the fish is unsure), but could be used under laboratory/controlled conditions to evaluate whether a compound affects animal physiology through PXR signaling when released to the media, as previously shown in other fish species (Fernandez et al. 2014, 2015; Gräns et al., 2015).

4. Conclusions

The full sequence of *pregnane X receptor* transcript has been determined in Senegalese sole, a marine ecotoxicology model species, and the conservation throughout vertebrate evolution of protein domains critical for PXR function has been confirmed. Sequence of the LBD of Senegalese sole PXR is highly divergent, and present knowledge can be used in future *in silico* and *in vitro* studies to gain insights on the affinity of old/new chemicals for ssPXR1. Levels and sites of *spxr* expression throughout development and in adult tissues has provided valuable information towards a better understanding of how PXR and its activating compounds may impact marine fish species physiology. In this regard, differential expression of *spxr1* in fish submitted to particular physiological circumstances evidenced a complex transcriptional regulation that should be considered if PXR is used as biomarker of xenobiotic exposure. Basic data (full PXR sequence and gene expression patterns) presented here will certainly foster the effectiveness of *in silico* and *in vitro* screening strategies to reduce the use of animals in experimentation to comply with the 2006 EU Registration, Evaluation, Authorization, and Restriction of

Chemicals (REACH) regulation through the incorporation of an environmental risk assessment approach with a more ecosystemic representation of the marine environments e.g. through the development of reporter assays using PXR sequences from different taxonomic groups.

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Author's contribution

CM and IF wrote the manuscript. IF designed the experiments. IF, CM, VR, LG and MT conducted the analyses and revised the data. PJG, VL and MLC contributed with reagents, equipment, materials and analytical tools. All authors edited and revised the manuscript.

Declaration of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interests and all of them have approved the final article.

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Figure 1. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of some vitamin D receptors (VDRs, NR1I), pregnane X receptors (PXR, NR1I2), and constitutive androstane receptors (CARs, NR1I3). The evolutionary history was inferred by using the Maximum Likelihood method based on the Poisson correction model (Zuckerkanndl and Pauling 1965). When the percentage of trees in which the associated taxa clustered together was higher or equal to 55, it is shown next to the main branches. A discrete Gamma distribution was used to model evolutionary rate differences among sites. The tree is drawn to scale, with branch lengths measured in the number of substitutions per site. The analysis involved 42 amino acid sequences. All positions with less than 95% site coverage were eliminated. There were a total of 332 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA7 (Kumar et al., 2016). *Caenorhabditis elegans* Nuclear hormone receptor (NHR)-1 sequence was used as outgroup to root the tree. CAR, constitutive androstane receptor; VDR, vitamin D receptor; PXR, pregnane X receptor. Scale represent n° of substitutions per site.

Figure 2. Multiple-sequence alignment of pregnane X receptors (PXR, NR1I2) protein sequences from human (*Homo sapiens*), mouse (*Mus musculus*), Western clawed frog (*Xenopus tropicalis*), zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), mummichog (*Fundulus heteroclitus*), Japanese puffer (*Takifugu rubripes*), Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) and Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). The amino acid sequence corresponding to the DNA binding domain (DBD) and the ligand binding domain (LBD) predicted by Pfam are indicated by blue boxes and green boxes, respectively. Over the alignment, fully conserved cysteine residues involved in the zinc binding site (black squares); and key residues for DNA binding (grey triangles), dimer interface (red ovals), heterodimer interface (black triangles), ligand binding (orange squares) and coactivator recognition (blue ovals) on Senegalese sole PXR sequence are indicated. The symbols dot, colon and asterisk at the bottom of the alignment reflect increasing conservation per residue in the aligned sequences.

Figure 3. Identified PXR Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) transcript variants in adult tissues. Amplified bands correspondent to transcript variants (A). On the left hand, transcript variant (*TransVar*) names and Size (nt); at the center amplified bands observed in a 2% agarose gel in intestine (*Int*) and ovaries (*Ov*) with SsPXRfw1-cds and SsPXRrev1-cds primers as well as O'GeneRuler™ 100bp Plus DNA Ladder (*M*); and with size (bp) at the right hand. Transcript variants graphical representation at scale (B). *Black box*, 5'UTR; *White box*, coding sequence showing corresponding sequences to DNA binding domain (*blue*) and ligand binding domain (*green*); *Grey box*, 3'UTR; *Arrows*, SsPXRfw1-cds and SsPXRrev1-cds primers anchor.

Figure 4. Relative gene expression of *pregnane X receptor (pxr)* throughout Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) development. Transcript levels of *sspXR1* variant were determined by qPCR from 3 technical replicates and normalized using *Ubiquitin (ubq)* gene expression. Levels at 18.5 hpf were used as reference and set to 1. *hpf*, hours post-fertilization; *dph*, days post-fertilization. Different letters over gene expression values denote significant differences among developmental stages (n=3; one-way ANOVA, Tukey multiple-comparison test; P < 0.05).

Figure 5. Relative gene expression of *pregnane X receptor (pxr)* in adult Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) tissues. Transcript levels of *ssprr1* variant were determined by qPCR from 3 technical replicates and normalized using *Ubiquitin (ubq)* gene expression. Levels in ovaries were used as reference and set to 1. Different letters over each histogram bar denote significant differences among tissues (n=3; one-way ANOVA, Tukey multiple-comparison test; $P < 0.05$).

Figure 6. Tissues and cell types from the cranial region showing *pregnane X receptor* (*pxr*) gene expression by *in situ* hybridization (ISH) in a 3 months old Senegalese sole. Expression of *sspXR1* and/or *sspXR2* variants was revealed at: brain, particularly at the olfactory lobe (a) and specifically on the granular layer (b); eye (c), specifically at the outer nuclear layer (Cn+Rn), inner nuclear layer and nerve fiber layer (d); mesenchymal (e) and cartilaginous tissue, particularly on chondrocytes from hyaline cartilage (f). From left to right: Hematoxylin-eosin (a, c, e, b, d, f), antisense riboprobe ('), sense riboprobe (') stainings. *Arrow heads* indicate ISH signal. *Amt*, adjacent mesenchymal tissue; *Crhc*, Cell rich hyaline cartilage; *Ce*, cone ellipsoids; *Ch*, chondrocytes; *Cn*, cone nucleus; *Gcl*, ganglion cell layer; *Gl*, Granular layer; *Hc*, horizontal cells; *In*, inner nuclear (layer); *Ip*, inner plexiform (layer); *L*, lens; *P*, pigment epithelium; *M*, muscle; *Nfl*, nerve fiber layer; *Rn*, rod nucleus. Scale bars represent 200 μm (a, c), 100 μm (e), 50 μm (d), and 20 μm (b, f).

Figure 7. Tissues and cell types from the vertebra, digestive system and spleen showing *pregnane X receptor (pxr)* gene expression by *in situ* hybridization (ISH) in a 3 months old Senegalese sole. Expression of *spxr1* and/or *spxr2* variants was revealed at: vertebral bodies (a), in particular at chondrocytes forming the neural arch (b); intestine and liver (c), specifically at the exocrine pancreas (d); spleen (e); and kidney (f). From left to right: Hematoxylin-eosin (a, c, e, b, d, f), antisense riboprobe (') , sense riboprobe (') staining. *Black arrow heads* indicate intense ISH signal, while *white arrow heads* diffuse ISH signal. *Ep*, exocrine pancreas; *Ht*, Hematopoietic tissue; *H*, hepatocytes; *In*, intestine; *Ebgz*, end-bone growth zones; *Fl*, fibrous layer; *Iv*, intervertebral space; *M*, muscle; *Na*, neural arch (insertion); *Ns*, neural spine; *Nt*, neural tube; *Ol*, osteogenic layer; *Rls*, ring-like structure; *S*, spleen; *T*, tubules (proximal and distal), *White asterisk*, bone. Scale bars represent 200 μm (c), 100 μm (a, e), 50 μm (f) and 20 μm (b, d).

Figure 8. Relative gene expression of *pregnane X receptor (pxr)* in juveniles of Senegalese sole (*Solea senegalensis*) under different nutritional conditions. Transcript levels of *spxr1* variant were determined by qPCR from 3 biological replicates and normalized using *Ubiquitin (ubq)* gene expression. Levels in Control group were used as reference and set to 1. *Left panel:* juveniles fed with 125VK₁ diet (Control); kept unfed (Fasting); exposed to 25 mg L⁻¹ of warfarin and fed with 125VK₁ diet (Warfarin); and/or being fed with 1250VK₁ diet (VK₁+) for 2 days. *Right panel:* juveniles fed with 125VK₁ diet for 5 days (Control); fed with 1250VK₁ diet during 3 days after being kept unfed for 2 days (Re-feeding); fed with 1250VK₁ diet during 3 days while being exposed to 25 mg L⁻¹ of warfarin (W rescue); and being fed with 1250VK₁ diet (VK₁+) for 5 days. Asterisk over each histogram bar denote significant differences between each experimental condition and the control group (n=3; Student's t-test; P < 0.05).

Table I. Designed primers for initial amplification of Senegalese sole PXR cDNA sequence, full-coding DNA sequence (cds) amplification, variants identification, relative gene expression and *in situ* hybridization probes.

Primer name	Component	5' to 3' nucleotide sequences	Expected amplicon size (bp)
SsF1PXR_deg	Forward	gagmtyaggaggaavaggatg	-
SsR1PXR_deg	Reverse	tcrttcatdstyctcatctc	-
SsF2PXR_deg	Forward	gacctcaccacvtreatgatc	-
SsR2PXR_deg	Reverse	caytccarakkccygy	-
SsF3PXR_deg	Forward	agccgctcctgctggagcct	-
SsR3PXR_deg	Reverse	ggkcctgttctcttcagtc	-
SsF4PXR_deg	Forward	ygttctcatgcaagycmtgtca	-
SsR4PXR_deg	Reverse	gccatcactttgggtagagcaart	-
SsPXRFw1-Marat	Forward	ggtgtacgagcgggttccagcca	-
SsPXRrev1-Marat	Reverse	tctgaccacactcccagatgtttg	-
SsPXRFw2-Marat	Forward	ttgctctgctcaaaggagccga	-
SsPXRrev2-Marat	Reverse	tagtagaagtggctggaacccgc	-
SsPXRFw3-Marat	Forward	ctgttcagatttcatacactacgc	-
SsPXRrev3-Marat	Reverse	cagccccagtctgcgtagtgtatga	-
SsPXRFw5-Marat	Forward	cagatccaggacatccagcctgacga	-
SsPXRrev5-Marat	Reverse	ccacacacaccacactctggactcg	-
SsPXRFw1-cds	Forward	atgagcgagggggccagt	1302
SsPXRrev1-cds	Reverse	gctgtatcagaagtcattacaggagtc	
SsPXRFw1-qpcr	Forward	gacgggtgtagcagcgggttc	118
SsPXRRev1-qpcr	Reverse	gggacatggcttgcatagagaaca	
SsPXRFw2-ISH	Forward	gagaaaaggttgaaaaagcagcg	678
SsPXRRev2-ISH	Reverse	tgttgaataggcgaggaggagc	

Supplementary Figure 1

Gene

Transcripts

Numbers at the top, exon number; *fh*, *Fundulus heteroclitus*; *on*, *Oreochromis niloticus*; *ss*, *Solea senegalensis*; *, predicted exons; Arrows, forward and reverse primer's location; Grey boxes, non-coding sequence; Black boxes, coding sequences, Blue boxes, DNA binding domain; Green boxes, ligand binding domain; Scale bar, 100 nt